

Effectiveness of Planned Teaching Program on Knowledge of Immediate Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive Devices (PPIUCD) among Antenatal Mothers in Selected Community Areas, Dehradun

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ABSTRACT

In the last few decades there has been a great progress in the understanding and armamentarium of contraception; many new ones have been developed. Some of the contraceptives are suitable at an individual level but at community level still the ideal contraceptive is elusive, the one which would cater to most of the couples. Couples need contraception throughout their reproductive years; initially it is required for delaying first pregnancy and later on for spacing and finally permanent methods when the family is complete. A pre-experimental study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching program on knowledge of immediate postpartum intrauterine contraceptive devices (PPIUCD) among antenatal mothers in selected community areas, Dehradun. An evaluative research approach with one group pretest and post-test Pre experimental design was used for this study. The sample consisted of 30 Antenatal mothers in selected community areas of Dehradun. They were selected by Non Probability purposive sampling technique. A structured knowledge questionnaire was used for the data collection. Data was analyzed and interpreted by using descriptive and inferential statistics. It shows that the enhancement of knowledge level 54.57 percent in the aspect of immediate PPIUCD with the pretest mean percentage 22.53% and post-test mean percentage 77.1%. The paired t-test value for immediate PPIUCD knowledge was 51.19 which suggest significant at $P < 0.05$ level, Hence stated research hypothesis (H1) was accepted. The demographic variable such as Educational status, Occupation and Monthly income shows statistical significant association with the pretest level of knowledge. Hence research hypothesis (H2) was accepted. The results show that the "Antenatal mothers knowledge level improved after implementation of the planned teaching program on immediate PPIUCD and the study indicates that the PTP is an effective method in improving moderate to adequate level of knowledge regarding health topics to the present day society where much attention is given to health promotion rather than treating the disease after acquiring it.

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KEYWORDS: PPIUCD, Knowledge, Planned Teaching Program, Effectiveness, Antenatal mothers

I. INTRODUCTION

"A good plan implemented today is better than a perfect plan implemented tomorrow."

-George Patton

India was the first country in the world to start its family planning program in 1952. The aim of the national program was population control so that economic development could keep pace with time. Contraception (both temporary and permanent) was one of the main prongs of this national program. Contraception is a highly cost effective public health measure and the most effective methods are also cost effective.

In the last few decades there has been a great progress in the understanding and armamentarium of contraception; many new ones have been developed. Some of the contraceptives are suitable at an individual level but at community level still the ideal contraceptive is elusive, the one which would cater

to most of the couples. Couples need contraception throughout their reproductive years; initially it is required for delaying first pregnancy and later on for spacing and finally permanent methods when the family is complete. The choice and decision of contraception should be left to them; popularly called 'Cafeteria Approach'. The couples should have adequate information about all the options available and they reach the informed decision on their own. Lack of adequate knowledge or wrong information and beliefs are common hurdles in acceptance of contraception. Fear of side effects and misconceptions is widespread and has been the most important explanation for non-use of contraception. In India, as in many other countries, postpartum family planning is usually initiated after 6 weeks postpartum. Early resumption of sexual activity coupled with early and unpredictable ovulation leads to many unwanted pregnancies in the first year postpartum. Moreover, in

developing countries particularly, women who once go back home after delivery do not return for even a routine postpartum check-up, leave aside contraception. This is maybe due to lack of education and awareness, social pressure, and non-access to facilities nearby.

Thus, immediate postpartum family planning services need to be emphasized where in the woman leaves the hospital with an effective contraception in place. Increase in hospital deliveries provides an excellent opportunity to sensitize women and provide effective contraception along with delivery services. An intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD) has several advantages for use in postpartum period as it is an effective, long term reversible contraception, is coitus independent, and does not interfere with breastfeeding. Postpartum IUCD (PPIUCD) insertion can be done post-placental that is within 10 min of placental expulsion, intra cesarean at the time of cesarean section or within 48 h of delivery. Inserting IUCD minutes after placental delivery is safe, will lead to wider usage of IUCD hence meeting the unmet needs of community. Contraception has been provided before assumption of sexual activity. It does not interfere with lactation and chances of perforation are almost nil due to thick walled uterus. Common menstrual abnormalities do not occur as many women as such have amenorrhoea or oligomenorrhoea during lactation period. The expulsion rates would be minimal if it was inserted by a trained provider and placed at the fundus.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To assess the pretest knowledge of immediate postpartum intrauterine contraceptive devices among antenatal mothers.
2. To administer the planned teaching program on immediate postpartum intrauterine contraceptive devices among antenatal mothers.
3. To evaluate the effectiveness of planned teaching program on knowledge of immediate postpartum intrauterine contraceptive devices among antenatal mothers.
4. To determine the association between pretest knowledge score with their demographic variables.

HYPOTHESES:

H1:-There is a significant difference between the mean pretest and post-test knowledge scores of antenatal mothers regarding knowledge of immediate Postpartum Intra Uterine Devices.

H2:-There is a significant association between the mean pretest knowledge scores on immediate Postpartum Intra Uterine Devices with selected demographic variables.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Research Approach

An evaluative research approach was used for this study.

Research Design

In the present study, pre-experimental (One group pre- test and post-test research design) was used.

Research Setting

This study was conducted in selected community areas of Dehradun.

Population

In this study accessible population are all the antenatal mothers residing in selected community areas of Dehradun.

Sample

The samples selected for this study are antenatal mothers in selected community area Badowala and Kadowala, Dehradun.

Sample Size

Sample size was 30 antenatal mothers living in selected community area Dehradun.

Sampling technique

Sample in this study were selected by using Non-Probability Purposive sampling technique.

Description of the tool

The tool used in the present study consist of following

A. Section-A

It comprised of eight items seeking information on demographic characteristics of the antenatal mothers such as, Age, religion, education status, occupation, type of family, income, no. of children and previous source of information.

B. Section-B

This part of the tool consists of thirty items from all the aspects of immediate PPIUCD.

The items were closed ended statements of Multiple choice type. The total score was Thirty. Each correct response carried 'one score'. The tool was prepared in English and Hindi.

The knowledge of the respondents was arbitrarily categorized into three categories:

Level of knowledge	Score
Inadequate	0 - 10
Moderate	11-21
Adequate	22-30

Description of PTP:

The PTP was entitled "Immediate PPIUCD among Antenatal mothers". The PTP was prepared to enhance the assessment knowledge of the Antenatal mothers regarding immediate PPIUCD.

It consist of the following content area.

- Different terminologies
- Contraceptive methods
- Postpartum family planning
- Postpartum IUCD
- Follow up care
- Postpartum family planning counselling.

Plan for data analysis

The data obtained was planned to be analyzed based on objectives and hypothesis of the study using descriptive and inferential statistics. Analyzed data is represented in the form of tables, graphs and figures.

Descriptive statistics:

Frequency and percentage were used to analyze the Demographic variable regarding immediate PPIUCD, such

as Age, Religion, education status, occupation, type of family, income, no. of children, and previous source of information.

- Mean, median and standard deviation was used to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme.

Inferential statistics:

- A. Paired t-test was used to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme (PTP) regarding immediate PPUCD on knowledge of Antenatal mothers.
- B. Chi-square was used to find association between the knowledge with their selected demographic variables. Level of significance is set at 0.05 to interpret the hypothesis and finding.

RESULTS:

The major findings of the study were as follows:

Section I: Distribution of respondents according to demographic variables.

According to their demographic details the majority of the respondent 15(50%) were in the age group between 26-30 years, 20(66.67%) were Hindu, 12(40%) has primary education, 18(60%) are housewife, 19(63.33%) were have nuclear family, 10(33.33%) were have monthly income 5000-10000 and 15001-20000 respectively, 18(60%) were prim gravida, 10(33.33%) have source of information from Internet/Newspaper/TV.

Section II: Comparison between pretest and posttest knowledge level.

TABLE (2):- Frequency and percentage distribution of Antenatal mothers knowledge level on immediate PPIUCD.

Knowledge level	Pretest		Post-test	
	f	%	f	%
Adequate	00	00%	22	73.33%
Moderate	07	23.33%	08	26.67%
Inadequate	23	76.67%	00	00%

Fig-1: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of Antenatal mothers according to their knowledge level on immediate PPIUCD.

Data in table 2 and fig-1 shows that the knowledge of Antenatal mothers regarding immediate PPIUCD. In the pretest 76.67% Antenatal mothers had inadequate knowledge; 23.33% had moderate knowledge and none of the Antenatal mothers had adequate knowledge in pre-test. In post-test 22 (73.33%) Antenatal mothers had adequate knowledge; 08 (26.67%) Antenatal mothers had moderate knowledge and none of the Antenatal mothers had inadequate knowledge in post-test.

Section III: Enhancement of knowledge scores on immediate PPIUCD.

Table3:- Aspect wise enhancement of knowledge scores on immediate PPIUCD.

Pretest			Posttest			Percentage of enhancement
Mean	Mean %	SD	Mean	Mean %	SD	
6.76	22.53	3.25	23.13	77.1	3.16	54.57

Fig-2:-Aspect wise enhancement of knowledge scores on immediate PPIUCD.

Table 3 and fig-2 reveals that the highest enhancement of knowledge 54.57 percent was seen in the aspect of immediate PPIUCD with the pretest mean percentage and post-test mean percentage of 22.53% and 77.1% respectively.

Section IV: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Paired t value of pretest and posttest knowledge scores.

Table4: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Paired t value of pretest and posttest knowledge scores.

COMPONENTS	PRETEST		POSTTEST		PAIRED't' value
	MEAN	SD	MEAN	SD	
Questionnaire on PPIUCD	6.76	3.25	23.13	3.160	51.19

Significant at 5% level of 29 df (i.e ,P<0.05)

The above table 4 represents the mean pre- test (6.76) and post-test (23.13) knowledge score regarding immediate PPIUCD. The paired t-test value for immediate PPIUCD knowledge value is 51.19. It was found to be significant at P<0.05 level, Hence research hypothesis (H₁) is accepted and null hypothesis was rejected. It evidence that the planned teaching program (PTP) is significantly effective on improving the knowledge of Antenatal mothers regarding immediate PPIUCD.

Section V: Association between pretest knowledge scores with their demographic variables

The results of chi-square analysis depicts that the demographic variable such as Educational status, Occupation and Monthly income shows statistical significant association with the pretest level of knowledge and there was no significant association of other demographic variables with their pretest level of knowledge. The obtained chi-square value of the variables such as Age ($\chi^2=0.95, P>0.05$), Religion ($\chi^2=0.18, P>0.05$), Educational status ($\chi^2=7.72, P>0.05$), Occupation ($\chi^2=17.28, P>0.05$), Type of family ($\chi^2=0.14, P>0.05$), Monthly income ($\chi^2=17.53, P>0.05$), Parity ($\chi^2=0.029, P>0.05$) and Source Of Information ($\chi^2=2.56, P>0.05$).

Hence research hypothesis (H₂) was accepted and null hypothesis was rejected.

CONCLUSION:

Despite making contraception widely available, there is poor acceptance of contraceptive methods either due to ignorance or fear of complications using them. Inadequate knowledge about contraceptive methods and incomplete or erroneous information about their use or where to procure them are the main reasons for not accepting family planning. Acceptance and continuation of IUCD can be increased by education and counseling. First step of any contraceptive implementation at the community level is to make the public aware and informed about the contraceptive. PPIUCD insertions via different routes (vaginal or caesarean) may have different outcomes at follow-up. There is minimal research comparing results between vaginal and caesarean insertions. Moreover, new understanding of this postpartum contraception necessitates examination of advantages and disadvantages of PPIUCD from a new perspective. In populations with family planning policies designed to increase contraceptive use; measuring the level contraceptive awareness also provides useful measure of success of information, education and communication activities and may help to identify program areas that need to be strengthened.

IMPLICATION:

The finding of the study had varied implications in different areas of nursing practice, nursing administration, nursing education and nursing research.

NURSING EDUCATION

The study would provide the guidelines to the nursing staff for developing health education programs for antenatal

mothers. In Community Health Nursing, health promotion being significant areas of primary, secondary and tertiary prevention. The nursing staff should be taught regarding immediate postpartum intrauterine devices and also should educate and advocate to act as consultants to antenatal mothers other individuals of the society. This is specifically of more significance in helping antenatal mothers at different community areas. This study will also make them understand about how nurses can promote antenatal mothers knowledge regarding PPIUCD so that they can guide the other individuals in the society at all the levels.

NURSING SERVICE:

Health promotion and prevention has been identified as fundamental concepts for nursing practice. Staff nurses' education has historically been in the domain of nursing. Nurses can recognize risk during postnatal period like unwanted pregnancy. So, nurses can take steps to prevent these from developing or prevent it before it is too late. The nurses can focus on many factors that can increase risk of unwanted pregnancies. Some of these risk factors can be changed, while others can't. Nurses are afforded wonderful understanding of health and wellness by which they can encourage antenatal mothers to assess their risk and helping them develop prevention strategies by using contraceptive measures and refer them as needed for follow up evaluation.

NURSING ADMINISTRATION:

The nursing administrators need to take initiatives in creative policies or plans in providing education to the antenatal and postnatal mothers in wards and as well as areas of different communities. In service education program to be conducted regularly for staff nurses who are working in maternal and child health department. The findings of the study can be used as a basis of training for health care personnel at various levels of health care systems.

NURSING RESEARCH

Several studies have been conducted on prevalence on unwanted pregnancies and acceptance of contraceptive devices but knowledge assessment of antenatal mothers regarding IUCD's have not been studied so extensively. There is a vast scope for exploration in this area. Findings of the study will act as a catalyst to carry out more extensive research on larger population in other different areas. The result of the study and tool used contributes to the body of knowledge of nursing. The tool and methodology used in this study would provide guidelines to the future researchers who are interested in conducting community based research.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- A Similar study may be conducted on a larger sample for wider generalization.
- A similar study may be replicated with control group
- A descriptive study can be conducted to find out the attitude and practice regarding immediate PPIUCD.
- The study may be conducted at different settings.

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